

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' MONOLOGUE SPEECH EXPRESSION SKILLS

*Sh. Atakulova*¹

Abstract:

The relevance of this problem is considered in the creative use of the project method to improve English language lessons. It is from school that the foundations of communication skills are laid, which students will certainly need throughout their educational activities. After all, the use of project methodology is an urgent task for all university and school teachers. So, the purpose of the study is to identify the possibilities of using the project method in developing monologue speech skills during English language lessons.

Key words: story, message, retelling, dialogue, monologue, volitional effort.

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Speech is varied. This is a conversation between friends, a passionate appeal from a speaker, a monologue from an artist, and a response from a student at the blackboard. In different situations, speech appears in different forms. Speech can be internal and external. Inner speech is mental speech, flowing, although on linguistic material, but without distinct external manifestations. It's like talking to yourself. It is fragmentary and lacks clear grammatical forms.

External speech is speech-communication, speech for others. It is designed for perception, for the speaker to be understood by his interlocutors or listeners. External speech can be dialogical or monological.

Dialogue is a conversation between two or more people. Each individual statement depends on the remarks of other interlocutors, on the situation. Dialogue does not require extended sentences, so it contains many incomplete sentences.

A monologue is the speech of one person, for example a story, message, retelling. Unlike dialogue, monologue is arbitrary, requires volitional effort, and sometimes significant preparatory work.

The speech of a particular person is a reflection of his general culture. Therefore, speech must meet certain requirements.

1. Correctness is compliance with the norms of modern literary language - grammar, spelling, punctuation. Correctness is considered the basic quality of good speech.

2. Clarity is its accessibility for others to understand. Words and expressions invented or taken from any work for decoration are detrimental to clarity.

3. Purity - free from vocabulary that is outside the boundaries of the literary language (jargon, dialectisms, parasite words).

4. Accuracy - the meaning of words and phrases used in speech is fully correlated with the semantic and objective aspects of speech.

5. Expressiveness - the ability to clearly, convincingly and at the same time, as concisely as possible, express one's thoughts and feelings, the ability to influence the addressee with intonation, choice of words, and construction of sentences.

¹ *Atakulova Shahlo Shamidullaevna, researcher, SamSU academic lyceum, Uzbekistan*

6. Richness - is determined by the choice of linguistic means to express the same thought, the absence of monotony, repetition of the same words and constructions.

External speech can appear in both oral and written form.

Written speech, in general, has the same features as oral speech, but they are more strictly expressed. At the same time, there are also distinctive features.

Firstly, written speech is always more complex and complete than oral speech, sentences are larger, constructions that complicate sentences are used more often, and there are more book words. Secondly, in the written version pauses, logical stresses, intonation, gestures and other means that play such an important role in oral speech are impossible. Thirdly, written language is limited by spelling. Fourthly, written speech is composed and flows much more slowly than oral speech. Fifthly, written speech is prepared speech, subject to testing, amenable to correction and improvement, therefore mastering written speech helps to improve the overall language culture.

At the beginning, students are taught reading, writing, oral and written speech - this is the formation of specific speech skills, that is, types of speech activity. Usually there are four main types of speech activity.

1. Reading
2. Listening.
3. Oral speech.
4. Written speech.

A person spends his entire life improving his speech and mastering the richness of the language. Speech arises from the need to speak out, and a person's statements are generated by certain motives. This aspect of speech activity is called speech motivation.

Speech motivation (for the sake of which I speak) arises in students when they have emotions associated with vivid impressions and interest in a particular activity. This means that the need for communication is the first condition for speech development. But communication is possible only with the help of generally understandable signs, that is, words, their combinations, and various turns of speech. Therefore, students need to be given speech samples or a speech environment created. This is the second condition for speech development. The richness and diversity of his own speech largely depends on the student's speech environment. Speech helps a student not only communicate with other people, but also explore the world. Mastering speech is a way of understanding reality. The richness of speech largely depends on the student's enrichment with various ideas and concepts, on his life experience. In other words, as speech develops, it needs not only linguistic, but also factual material. This is the third condition for successful speech development.

Thus, many scientists have been involved in speech research, each of whom has made a direct contribution to the development of exercise systems for the development of oral and written speech. The content and form of a person's speech depend on his age, situation, experience, temperament, character, abilities, interests, conditions. With the help of speech, students study educational material, communicate, influence each other and influence themselves in the process of self-suggestion. The more actively students improve oral, written and other types of speech and expand their vocabulary, the better the level of their cognitive abilities and culture.

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